
An Analysis of Indian Homegrown Clothing Brands from the Perspective of Youth Consumption

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Abstract:

Homegrown clothing brands have gained popularity in India over the past few years, despite the fashion industry being predominantly dominated by foreign brands. This study aims to analyse the strengths of homegrown clothing brands in India from the youth's perspective, examining consumer loyalty and personal experiences with these brands. A mixed-methods approach was used, employing multiple regression, the cumulative link model, and text sentiment analysis for statistical analysis. The study found that price, uniqueness and personalisation, brand image, ethical practices and quality of the product have a significant impact on consumers' decision to shop from homegrown brands.

Keywords: Homegrown, Clothing, Youth Consumption, Price, Quality

Introduction:

Over the last decade, homegrown brands in India have gained significant attention, as young consumers increasingly shift away from foreign brands. This shift has been driven by a growing preference for uniqueness and personalization, pricing, and quality of the product. In the fiscal year 2024-25, the budget allocated to the textile industry has increased by 28%.

The fashion industry in India which was once highly influenced by foreign brands is now seeing an emergence of homegrown brands. The industry which was once dictated by one of its major factors being status symbol- 'Articles of Snob Appeal' has now been overshadowed by the factor of quality of the product with the consumers now being more aware of their fashion choices.

While there are studies which evaluated sustainability, attitudes towards foreign and homegrown brands, and challenges of homegrown clothing brands, there is limited information which focuses on strengths of homegrown brands from students' perspective. Homegrown brands are those brands that originate and are developed in a country. In this paper, we refer to Indian made textile brands in the homegrown category.

The study aims to examine the strengths of homegrown brands from students' perspective, focusing on uniqueness and personalisation, quality, and price. By assessing students' perspective this research aids homegrown brands to focus on factors that can help them strengthen their consumer base and foster brand loyalty, which will help them grow.

Literature Review:

1. Anjali Awasthi, Charu Swami (2023) Sustainable Fashion in Indian Context: An Analysis- International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research
The research paper discusses sustainability in the fashion industry, focusing on the changing perception of consumers toward the fashion industry in India. It highlights that people are now more conscious of their purchases and are shifting toward environmentally friendly options, social responsibility, and products with a unique and personalized touch. Additionally, consumers are becoming more open to trying homegrown brands. The paper also examines the SURE initiative launched by the Ministry of Textiles, which aims to make the Indian clothing industry more sustainable.
2. Dr. K. Balanaga Gurunathan, M. Krishnakumar (2013) Factors Influencing Apparel Buying Behaviour in India: A Measurement Model- Indian Journal of Research
This research, conducted in Coimbatore, examines the factors influencing apparel buying behaviour in India. It highlights how certain factors significantly impact consumer choices, emphasizing the importance of ready-made garments, membership benefits, and brand consciousness in shaping consumer preferences. The study also explores various methods to enhance customer engagement and brand loyalty. However, its findings are limited due to the focus on a single city and a small sample size.
3. Naveen Arora (2017) Growth of Small Brands: A Perspective of Indian Clothing Industry- International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research
This paper evaluates the factors that contribute to the growth of small clothing brands in India. It discusses how brand growth is determined by various factors, such as product availability and perceived product quality. The use of effective marketing strategies, including sales promotions and advertisements, also plays a crucial role. Additionally, utilizing different distribution channels, such as online platforms and franchise stores, has proven to be highly successful for brands

Research Objectives:

This study examines the strengths of homegrown clothing brands from the students' perspective, focusing on various factors like affordability, sustainability, quality of the product, etc. The key research questions include:

1. What are the strengths of homegrown clothing brands according to the youth's perspective?
2. What factors impact consumer's brand loyalty?
3. How do consumers perceive and experience homegrown clothing brands in India?

Hypothesis:**Null Hypothesis(H₀):**

Brand image, use of ethical practices, price, quality, uniqueness and personalisation of the product do not significantly impact students' decision when purchasing from a homegrown brand.

Alternate Hypothesis(H₁):

Brand image, use of ethical practices, price, quality, uniqueness and personalisation of the product significantly impacts students' decision when purchasing from a homegrown brand.

Methodology:

The research methodology of a paper is very important because it shows the validity, reliability and transparency of a paper. In this study we have used primary data which led us to use in-depth study of the phenomenon.

Sampling Technique:

The data was collected through a survey distributed online to 400+ students across various cities, mainly Jaipur and Mumbai. The survey had multiple choice questions and one open-ended question at the end. The survey evaluated how students perceive homegrown brands and their strengths.

A total of 382 participants aged 15-24, were selected using a purposive sampling technique. This sample was chosen as it represents the youth of the nation and is seen to be using homegrown brands more frequently. This study makes use of both, quantitative and qualitative data collection technique. Our primary source of data is used by collecting surveys. The open-ended question in the survey has added to the qualitative aspect of data collection. The survey responses were evaluated using inferential statistical methods like cumulative link models (CLM) and multiple regression, descriptive statistics techniques were also used to analyse the graphs and charts of the data. Text sentiment analysis was used to study the qualitative aspect of the survey. All these tests were run on R Studio.

This approach has helped us not only to get structured data, which is measurable, comparable and is an effective technique for statistical analysis but also has given us an insight on the personal experiences of the consumers. Participants provided informed consent and voluntarily participated. Their data will be anonymous to protect their identity and ensure confidentiality.

Results and Analysis:

What are the strengths of homegrown clothing brands according to the youth's perspective?

Multiple regression (1) and analysis of graphs examined the above question which made use of inferential statistics and descriptive statistical technique.

To examine what factors influence the consumer's decision to shop from homegrown brands over foreign brands, our survey had a question which evaluated the factors which affect consumer's purchasing decisions.

To develop a model for multiple regression, we need both dependent and independent variables. The specific reason to take purchasing patterns as the dependent variable is to see if the chosen independent variables make a difference, i.e., lead to the actual purchase. Given below in the Table 1.1 are the dependent and independent factors for the model.

Dependent Variables	Independent Variables
1. Shopping from homegrown brands	Price Uniqueness and Personalisation Brand name Sustainability/Eco-friendliness Supporting local businesses Quality and Craftsmanship of the product Brand reputation and image Marketing strategy Cultural Significance Ethical practices

Table 1.1

The multiple regression model used to answer this question is:

Shopping from home grown brands

$$= \alpha + \beta_1(\text{price}) + \beta_2(\text{uniqueness and personalisation}) + \beta_3(\text{brand name}) + \beta_4(\text{sustainability/ eco – friendliness}) + \beta_5(\text{supporting local businesses}) + \beta_6(\text{quality and craftsmanship of product}) + \beta_7(\text{brand reputation and image}) + \beta_8(\text{marketing strategy}) + \beta_9(\text{cultural significance}) + \beta_{10}(\text{ethical practices})$$

- **Shopping from homegrown brands** is the dependent variable
- α is the intercept (it is the value of dependent variable when all the independent variables are 0).
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{10}$ are the independent variables.
- **Note:** β_6 (quality and craftsmanship of product) was normalised using reverse log transformation.

By analysing the graphs of all the factors, we deduced that all of them nearly had normal distribution except quality and craftsmanship of product. β_6 (quality and craftsmanship of product) was transformed as the graph for this data was strongly negatively skewed. It was necessary as regression assumes normal distribution in the data. The graph for the same is given below.

1.1 Graph for quality and craftsmanship of product:

After trying multiple permutations and combinations for this model by using intersection of two or more variables, we conclude that it is an appropriate model for the data as it has the highest R-Square amongst all the models being 15.93%. This model even had an F-statistic, i.e., 7.029 is greater than 5 and a p-value, i.e., 3.96e-10 is less than 0.05 which implies that this model is significant. Also, this model takes into consideration all the factors assessed in the survey.

Variable	t value	Pr(> t)
Intercept	6.593	1.48E-10
Price	4.314	2.06E-05
Uniqueness and personalisation	2.011	0.0451
Brandimage	1.656	0.0986
Ethicalpractices	1.867	0.0626
Quality_1(β_6)	1.691	0.0917

Table1.2

The above table (TABLE 1.2) helps us understand the most significant factor influencing the purchasing pattern is price, followed by uniqueness, ethical practices, quality and craftsmanship of the product, and brand image respectively by analysing the p-value and t-value.

lm(shopping_H ~ price + uniqueness + sustainability + brandimage + brandnam ...

1.2 Q-Q (Quantile-Quantile) Plot:

The Q-Q (1.2) plot assesses whether the data followed normal distribution or not, i.e., checks for linearity. By examining the Q-Q plot, we can infer that the data follows a normal distribution.

lm(shopping_H ~ price + uniqueness + sustainability + brandimage + brandnam ...

1.3 Residual vs Leverage:

The residual vs leverage graph (1.3) helps to detect the outliers. By examining the graph, we deduce that there are only 3 outliers out of 382 sampled responses from the data.

Variance Inflation Factor	Value
Price	1.308752
Uniqueness	1.609723
Sustainability	1.868347
Brandimage	2.145646
Brandname	1.683637
quality_1	1.727256
Localbusiness	1.882268
Marketing strategy	1.462859
Culturalsignificance	2.019381
Ethicalpractices	2.119799

Table 1.3

The above table (TABLE 1.3) mentions the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for all the independent variables. It helps to assess if there is multi-collinearity amongst the variables. As the VIF for all the factors is less than 5 we can deduce that there is a little or no multi-collinearity amongst the variables.

Based on the observations from the graphs and statistical findings from the tables, we reject the null hypothesis(H_0) and alternate hypothesis (H_1) is accepted.

What factors impact consumer's brand loyalty?

Cumulative Link Model (CLM) examined the above question which made use of inferential statistics.

To examine what factors influence the consumer's decision to be loyal to a brand, our survey had a question which evaluated the factors which affect consumer's brand loyalty.

To develop a model for a classical linear model, we need both dependent and independent variables. The specific reason to take brand loyalty as the dependent variable is because brand loyalty helps determine the impact of other factors, i.e., independent variables have on it. Given below in the Table 1.4 are the dependent and independent factors for the model. The reason that we do not need to normalise the data is because the classical linear model is only used for ordinal data.

Dependent Variables	Independent Variables
1. Brand Loyalty	Price Quality Design Customer Service Brand Reputation

Table 1.4

Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) a summary statistic used in comparing the relative goodness of fit of two or more models for a given set of data, while taking into account the number of parameters in each model. The model with the lowest AIC is considered the best among all models specified-(APA). After trying multiple permutation and combinations for this model by using tests for ordinal data, we come to a conclusion that CLM is an appropriate fit for this data as it has given us the lowest AIC, 712.62.

Variance Covariance Matrix:

A square matrix that represents how variance in each variable in a set is related to variance in all other variables in the set. The covariances between pairs of variables are located at the intersection of the row and column that correspond to the two variables. The quantities along the diagonal of the matrix are variances rather than covariances.

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
price	-0.038006	0.052419	-0.725	0.46888
quality	0.014041	0.067426	0.208	0.83515
design	0.003785	0.067478	0.056	0.9553
customerservice	-0.156282	0.055685	-2.807	0.00527
brandreputation	0.152872	0.054239	2.818	0.00508

Table1.5

In the table (TABLE 1.5), the low off-diagonal values and stable variances shown in the table suggests that there is no severe multicollinearity in the model.

Predictor	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	Significance
Brandreputation	0.47345	0.12606	3.756	0.000173	Highly Significant ($p < 0.001$)

Table 1.6

We can see that after evaluating all the factors using CLM like p-value, z-value, etc. from table 1.6, brand reputation has played a crucial role for consumers to stay loyal to the brand.

Text Sentiment Analysis:

Text sentiment analysis is a natural language processing (NLP) technique used to analyse words and classify the sentiments as positive, negative and neutral. The following steps were used to analyse the data:

1. Text preprocessing
 - i. Tokenization: It involves splitting of texts into tokens, i.e., words
 - ii. Stop words removal: It involves removing words like ‘and’, ‘is’, ‘the’, etc.
 - iii. Special words removal: It involves removing specific words like ‘brands’, ‘clothing’, ‘brand’, ‘homegrown’, ‘foreign’, ‘india’, and ‘indian’
2. Word frequency analysis and Word Cloud

Word frequency analysis and word cloud highlights the words that have been repeated the most. Word frequency analysis is numerical and tabular representation while word cloud is a visual and pictorial representation.

Rank	Keyword	Count
1	Quality	32
2	Affordable	21
3	Unique	17
4	Local	16
5	Designs	15
6	Nice	13
7	Experience	12
8	Feel	10
9	Support	10
10	Pretty	8
11	they're	8
12	Culture	7
13	Design	7
14	Market	7
15	Price	7
16	Cultural	6
17	Products	6
18	Sustainability	6
19	Variety	6
20	Amazing	5

Table 1.7

Word Cloud:

By analysing the table (TABLE 1.7) and the word cloud, we can observe that words like “quality, affordable, unique and local” have an impact. So, we can deduce that affordability, quality, uniqueness and local or made in India plays a crucial role in consumer experiences and influences their perception about the homegrown brands.

3. Sentiment Analysis:

Sentiment analysis helps to understand the tone of the words. It can be positive, negative and neutral. Using RStudio, we created sentiment analysis histogram Graph 1.3 and table of quartiles (TABLE 1.8) for the same.

Graph 1.3 Sentiment Analysis

Statistic	Value
Min	-1.6
1st Qu.	0.5
Median	0.8
Mean	1.327
3rd Qu.	1.8
Max	8.5

Table 1.8

By examining the histogram and the table (TABLE 1.8), we can observe that there is a mix of perception. The mean of the data is 1.327 and the median is 0.8 which suggests that data is neutral to slightly positive. Max value 8.5 suggests high satisfaction while -1.6 suggests low

satisfaction. Hence, we can conclude that overall experience of homegrown brands has been good for people.

NOTE: For the text sentiment analysis, the data set has only 156 variables to perform any statistical analysis on it. It was because out of 382 respondents only 156 responded for the open-ended question.

4. Actual comments extracted from the data:

Following are the actual comments from the data set.

Positive

[1]"not very known to a lot of brands and my last experience was very good

[2] "I find them better than foreign ones"

[3] "It's great"

[4] "They are affordable and meet the needs of the expectations of the consumers which is what makes them so unique."

Negative

[1]"Homegrown clothing brands are on a rise but they fail to effectively compete against foreign brands as though they help small businesses, their small scale production units make them more expensive in comparison to foreign brands which affects their demand as people aren't able to buy the clothes at higher prices."

Limitations:

While this study provides insight into the strengths of homegrown brands from a consumer's perspective, there are certain limitations that have been addressed below.

Firstly, its scope is limited as the data was of students only from Mumbai and Jaipur.

Secondly, even the sample size was not large enough as we only had 382 people in our final data set on which we had run the tests.

Lastly, the R-Square in the multiple regression model was low (15.93%). It means that only 15.93% data is explained by this model. It is low because consumer behaviour is subjective and there are many factors other than those considered that affect consumers' choice.

Conclusion:

This paper aimed to analyse the strengths of homegrown clothing brands in India from the perspective of youth consumption. While previous studies have explored sustainability, attitudes toward foreign and homegrown brands, and the challenges faced by homegrown brands, there is limited research focusing specifically on their strengths from a student's perspective. The findings indicate that factors such as price, uniqueness, ethical practices, product quality and craftsmanship, brand image, and brand loyalty play a crucial role in consumers' decision-making when choosing homegrown brands. These insights offer valuable guidance for homegrown brands aiming to strengthen their market position, enhance brand loyalty, and ensure positive consumer experiences. Future research could broaden the scope by examining larger and more diverse demographics across more cities. Understanding youth preferences and perceptions is critical for homegrown brands to thrive in the competitive market.

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